

PLANNING OF BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP ACTIVITIES

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KEYWORDS

Plan, planning, business plan,
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ABSTRACT

Why is a business plan necessary? Strategic planning of small business activities, strategic planning, goals, objectives, strategy, how to implement and control the activity of a small business enterprise determines the amount of profit from this business. This should be considered and planned in advance. Clearly defining the goal in planning is the key to the success of a small business.

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BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI REJALASHTIRISH

KALIT SO‘ZLAR:

Reja, rejalashtirish, biznes reja iqtisodiy tahlil, operativ tahlil, strategik tahlil, samaradorlik, samaradorlik tahlili, kutilayotgan samara va natija

ANNOTATSIYA

Biznes-reja nima uchun zarur? Kichik biznes faoliyatini strategik rejalashtirish, strategik rejalashtirish, kichik biznes korxonasi faoliyatini maqsadi, vazifalari, strategiyasi, uni qanday amalga oshirish va nazorat qilinishi ushbu biznesdan keladigan foyda miqdorini belgilaydi. Buni oldindan ko‘rib chiqish va rejalashtirish lozim. Rejalashtirishda maqsadni aniq belgilab olish – kichik biznes muvaffaqiyatining garovidir.

Biznes-reja nima uchun zarur?

- yangi biznesni boshlash uchun;
- o‘z biznesingizni kengaytirish uchun;
- uni boshqa shaxsga o‘tkazish yoki sotish uchun;
- ssuda olish uchun.

Ko‘pincha oxirgi sababni muhim deb biladilar. Aslida bunday emas. Biznesingiz bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan eng muhim narsa, ayniqsa, kimningdir pulini olish xoxishida, bu - menejment. Kiskasi - bu Sizsiz. Ko‘pgina tad- birkorlarni Biznes-rejani tuzish yo‘lidagi dastlabki harakatlariga faqat bi-rinchi sabab etaklab boradi. Biznes-reja turli xil biznesmenlar, tadbirkorlar, korxonalar, firmalari yoki turli xil mulk shakllarida bo‘lib turli xil xizmatlarni bajarish, har xil si- fatdagi, hajmdagi, turlicha vaqtda maxsus ishlab chiqarishga xoxishi bo‘lgan xodimlarga nisbatan tatbiq etiladi. Biznes olamida tug‘ilgan yangi fikrlarni, yangi xoxishni o‘z vaqtida saqlab qolib, uni haqiqatga aylantirish foydadan holi bo‘lmaydi. Biznes sohasidagi yangi fikrlar miyaga har qanday sharoit va holatda kelishi mum- kin. Masalan, nonushta vaqtida yoki samolyotda uchayotganingizda, ta’tilda, plyajda chumilish vaqtida yoki muvaffaqiyatsizlikka uchraganda va hokazo. Shundan so‘ng, munozaralar, izlanishlar, o‘z-o‘zini tahlil qilish va boshqalardan so‘rab-surishtirishlar jarayonida bu fikr kurtak otadi. Lekin bu ko‘rtakning navda otib, 18 meva berish uchun haddan tashqari faol ishlash talab etiladi. Ko‘rtakdan farqli ularoq yangi biznes tabiiy ravishda o‘z-o‘zidan rivojlanib ketavermaydi. Ko‘pincha asoslanmagan yangi biznes o‘nib chiqquncha nobud bo‘lib ketadi. Amaliyotda yashab qolgan bizneslar mi- qdori 20% ni tashkil etadi. Yangi biznesning hayotini saqlab qolish imkoni- yati o‘z qo‘lingizda - faqat biznes-rejani to‘g‘ri tayyorlash lozim. Biznes-reja eng boshidan qattiq va ishonchli poydevorga o‘rnatilishi zarur. Agar siz shunday rejasiz ish boshlasangiz o‘zingiz mo‘ljallagan narsaga erisha olmay qolishingiz mumkin.

Strategik rejalashtirish konsepsiyasining mohiyati kelajakka mo‘ljallanganligidadir, iqtisodiyot rivojidagi yuqori darajali noaniqlikni hisobga oladi, ulkan sifatli maqsadlarga erishishga yo‘naltirilgan, boshqaruvga yondoshishning variantlari ko‘p bo‘lishini talab

etadi. Oldiga qo'yilgan maqsadlar va erishilgan natijalar o'rtasidagi uzilishni oldindan nazarda tutadi.

Strategik rejalashtirishning uzoq muddatli rejadan asosiy farqi shundaki, strategik rivojlantirishda o'tmishda belgilangan rivojlanish tendensiyalaridan foydalanishning imkoni yo'q. Bu yerda barcha marketing xavf-xatarlari va imkoniyatlarini taxlil qilish hamda baholashga alohida o'rin ajratiladi. Kichik biznesda strategik rejalashtirishda iqtisodiy-matematik usullar modellar keng ishlatiladi.

Firmaning strategiyasi-umumiy harakatlar rejasi, uning yordamida firma o'z maqsadlariga erishishga intiladi (maqsadlarga yetishish algoritmi).

Kichik biznes strategiyasi-firma strategiyasining asosiy qismini detallashtirish, bozordagi faoliyatining miqdor va sifat ko'rsatkichlari hamda yo'nalishlarining yig'indisidan va firma strategiyasini to'liqroq amalga oshirish mumkin bo'lgan marketingning alohida chora-tadbirlariga yo'naltiruvchi prinsipial qarorlardan iboratdir.

Strategik reja-operatsiyalar yig'indisi bo'lib, firma rahbarining nuqtai nazaridan qaraganda ularni bajarish uning strategiyasini amalga oshirishga olib keladi.

Taktika qisqa muddatli davrga (masalan: yil, chorak, oy) ishlab chiqiladi va zarur bo'lganda, biznesning strategik vazifalarini hal qilish maqsadida to'g'rilab chiqiladi. Samarali strategik rejani tuzish quyidagilarni bosqichma bosqich amalga oshirishni talab qiladi: firma maqsadini aniq belgilab olish; bozordagi raqobot holatini, distribyutor va maxsulot yetkazib beruvchilar, ularning moliyaviy xolatini o'z ichiga oluvchi biznes olib borish shart -sharoitlarini tahlil qilish; biznes faoliyatini va uni ishlab chiqarishga qo'shib ketishi jarayonini aniq ko'z oldiga keltirish ; tashqi xavf va ustunliklarni, ichki imkoniyat va nozik jihatlarni, raqobot ustunliklarni ko'rib chiqish. Xavf va ustunliklarni, ichki imkoniyat va nozik jihatlarni tekshirish SWOT tahlil deb ataladi va undan kichik/katta biznesni rejalashtirishda foydalaniladi.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish mumkinki rejalashtirish bu boshqaruv jarayonining dastlabki bosqichlaridan biri bo'lib, u maqsadni amalga oshirish, rivojlantirishda yo'nalishni belgilash demakdir. Har qanday firma o'z faoliyatini puxta va yaxshi rejalashtirishi kerak chunki, firmaning omon qolishi va foyda ko'rishi shunga bog'liq bo'ladi. Rejalashtirishda maqsadni aniq belgilash, biznes loyihalarini texnik-iqtisodiy asoslash, maslahatchilar xizmatidan foydalanish katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Kichik biznesga tadbirkorlik loyihalarining taqrizchilarni jalb etish, ayniqsa, muhimdir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Xaydarov B., Saitov S. Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollari. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 634-635.

2. Xaydarov B. X., Saitov S. A. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT TUSHUNCHASI, AFZALLIKLARI AMALIY AHAMIYATI VA XORIJIY TAJRIBA //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 5. – C. 151-156.

3. Хайдаров Б. ИҚТИСОДИЙ ИСЛОҲОТЛАРНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШДА КАМБАҒАЛЛИКНИ ҚИСҚАРТИРИШ //Экономика и образование. – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 288-292.
4. Бахром Х. Х. БИЗНЕСНИ РЕЖАЛАШТИРИШ ТАРТИБЛАРИ //PEDAGOGS jurnali. – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 2. – С. 139-142.
5. Nodira T., Haydarov B., Zafar Q. THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF COMPETITION AND MONOPOLY IN THE ECONOMY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 241-245.
6. Haydarov B. IMPACT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY PROTECTION ON THE DIGITAL ECONOMY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 163-174.
7. Nodira T., Haydarov B., Zafar Q. THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF COMPETITION AND MONOPOLY IN THE ECONOMY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 241-245.
8. Haydarov Baxrom Xolmuradovich, Xudayarov Rashid Tuychiyevich. (2022). RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT BIZNESNI REJALASHTIRISH. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 1(2), 110–113. Retrieved from <http://journal.jbnuu.uz/index.php/ijcstr/article/view/130>
9. Haydarov Baxrom Xolmuradovich, & Saitov Sirojiddin Abduvalievich. (2022). RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA KICHIK BIZNESNING O'RNI. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 1(2), 113–116. Retrieved from <http://journal.jbnuu.uz/index.php/ijcstr/article/view/131>
10. Haydarov Baxrom Xolmuradovich. (2022). RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA BUXGALTERIYA VA AUDITNI O'RNI. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 1(2), 128–131. Retrieved from <http://journal.jbnuu.uz/index.php/ijcstr/article/view/135>
11. Худаяров Р., Ахром А. БОЛЬШИЕ ДАННЫЕ ТИПОВ СИСТЕМЫ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ИХ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ В ДАННОЙ ОБЛАСТИ // Журнал академических исследований и тенденций в области педагогических наук. – 2022. – Т. 1. – No 4. – С. 21-24.
12. Худояров Р. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ В УСЛОВИЯХ РЫНОЧНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ // Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – No 2. – С. 610-612.
13. Nizametdinov A. et al. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY TODAY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 251-254.
14. Sirojiddin S., Azizbek A. TRANSITION TO THE MARKET ECONOMY AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS IN UZBEKISTAN //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 255-258.

15. Sirojiddin S., Nodira T., Dinora S. CHARACTERISTICS OF PRICE AND FORMATION //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 265-270.

16. Akramovich N. A. THE PRIORITY OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE AGRICULTURAL EDUCATION SYSTEM //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 10. – C. 185-191.

17. Nizametdinov A., Ahmedova H. Elektron ta 'lim metodologiyasi rivojlantirishning usullari //Zamonaviy innovatsion tadqiqotlarning dolzarb muammolari va rivojlanish tendensiyalari: yechimlar va istiqbollar. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 29-31.

18. Nizametdinov, A. A. (2022). OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA AGRAR SOHANING USTUVORLIGI UNDA INNOVATSIYALARNING QULLANISHI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1(6), 96–98. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/cf/article/view/104>

19. Nizametdinov, A. A. (2022). OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMINING AGRAR SOHASIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR QO'LLASH USTUVORLIGI. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES, 1(6), 58–60. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/cf/article/view/96>

20. Akramovich N. A. HISTORY, SUBJECT AND OBJECT OF FORMATION OF" MACROECONOMICS" //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 10. – №. 1. – C. 209-210.

21. Nizametdinov A. et al. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY TODAY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 251-254.

22. Akramovich N. A. et al. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI O'ZBEKISTONDAGI O'RNI //Conferencea. – 2022. – C. 67-69.

23. Nizametdinov Ali Akramovich. (2022). SUN'IY INTELEKTNI KADRLAR SIYOSATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI AHAMIYATI. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 1(2), 251–253. Retrieved from <http://journal.jbnuu.uz/index.php/ijcstr/article/view/171>